

Supplementary Documents

Holt-Winters configuration - Prompt:

```
prompt = (  
  
"You are configuring a Holt-Winters model (Exponential  
Smoothing) for monthly energy consumption.\n"  
  
"Your goal is to decide whether the seasonal component should  
be:\n"  
  
"- 'add' if the seasonal amplitude is roughly constant\n"  
  
"- 'mul' if the seasonal amplitude increases with the level of  
the series\n\n"  
  
"Base your decision on the following statistics:\n"  
  
f"- Mean: {stats['mean']}\n"  
  
f"- Standard deviation: {stats['std']}\n"  
  
f"- ACF (lag 12): {stats['acf_lag12']}\n"  
  
f"- Trend slope: {stats['trend_slope']}\n\n"  
  
"Return ONLY a valid JSON object with the fields:\n"  
  
"- seasonal (either 'add' or 'mul')\n"  
  
"- seasonal_periods (assume 12 for monthly data)\n"  
  
)
```

LSTM configuration - Prompt:

```
prompt = (  
  
"The residuals from a statistical model show the following  
statistics:\n"  
  
f"- Mean: {residual_stats['mean']}\n"  
  
f"- Standard deviation: {residual_stats['std']}\n"  
  
f"- Skewness: {residual_stats['skew']}\n"  
  
f"- Kurtosis: {residual_stats['kurtosis']}\n"  
  
f"- ACF (lag 6): {residual_stats['acf_lag6']}\n"  
  
f"- PACF (lag 1): {residual_stats['pacf_lag1']}\n\n"  
  
"Suggest a suitable LSTM configuration to model these  
residuals.\n"  
  
"The time_steps value should be at least 12 to ensure meaningful  
temporal learning.\n"  
  
"Even if the residuals resemble weak or noisy signals,  
prioritise configurations that are sensitive to subtle temporal  
patterns.\n"  
  
"Always use 'tanh' as activation to allow both positive and  
negative residual prediction.\n"  
  
"Choose the number of neurons dynamically based on the structure  
detected in the residuals.\n\n"  
  
"Return ONLY a valid JSON object with the fields: time_steps,  
neurons, activation, dropout."  
  
)
```

Monthly forecast analysis - Prompt:

```
prompt = (  
  
f"You are preparing a short managerial report for  
{location}.\n\n"  
  
"First, write a single paragraph summarising the energy forecast  
changes month by month compared to the same months last year. "  
  
"Do not use bullet points. Just focus on summarising the relative  
increases and decreases in a clear, fluid narrative.\n\n"  
  
"Then, in a second paragraph, explain how the local  
characteristics of this region – such as climate, seasonal  
demand variation, "  
  
"or urban versus rural dynamics – might help contextualise these  
variations.\n\n"  
  
"Each line below shows the forecasted consumption for a month,  
followed by the actual value from the previous year, "  
  
"and the percentage difference:\n"  
  
+ "\n".join(text_lines)  
  
)
```

Residual commentary - Prompt:

```
prompt = (  
  
f"The LSTM component of the GenEneCast model produced the  
following residual corrections: {values}. "  
  
f"The model's validation performance showed an RMSE of  
{rmse:.2f} and a MAE of {mae:.2f}. "  
  
"These values represent how much the forecast deviates from the  
actual observed consumption. "  
  
"Write a single, concise paragraph summarising the overall  
behaviour of the residuals and the implications of these error  
metrics. "  
  
"Avoid technical jargon. Focus on what these numbers suggest  
about the model's reliability for decision-makers."  
  
)
```